

A Geth-based detection system for ERC20 honeypot contract in Ethereum

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Abstract

As decentralized finance (DeFi) expands and decentralized exchanges (DEXs) proliferate, the security of smart contracts and blockchain transactions on Ethereum is attracting heightened scholarly attention. With the introduction of the ERC20 (fungible token standard), numerous honeypot ERC20 contracts have emerged within the Ethereum blockchain. Since DEXs permit the deployment of any token adhering to the ERC20 standard, a substantial number of honeypot contracts designed to steal trader assets have proliferated. Specifically, users exchange valuable tokens (e.g., ETH) for honeypot ERC20 tokens but are unable to exchange these honeypot tokens back for ETH, resulting in financial losses for traders. This study proposes a lightweight honeypot contract detection system that can be integrated into the go-Ethereum client (Geth). Unlike previous work, our detector does not rely on contract interaction records or source code provided by contract creators. Instead, it implements static data flow analysis on contract bytecode to infer the mechanisms of honeypot within the contract. Furthermore, as a lightweight detector integrated into the Ethereum client, it focuses solely on the control flow of the ERC20 standard Transfer method, providing a rapid analysis advantage over existing methods that analyze contracts in their entirety, with an average detection time of 9.74 milliseconds per contract. Ex-

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periments conducted on contracts known to exhibit honeypot behavior and real-world token contracts have demonstrated the effectiveness of our tool in identifying honeypot ERC20 contracts.

Keywords: Blockchain, Ethereum, Smart contract, Honeypot, Static analysis

1. Introduction

Ethereum[1] launched its mainnet in July 2015. While its design was influenced by Bitcoin's transactional model based on unspent transaction outputs (UTXO)[2], Ethereum adopted an account-based transactional model and introduced programs, smart contracts, which could run on the blockchain. On the Ethereum mainnet, smart contracts allow anyone to deploy permanent, immutable decentralized applications executed by the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM). Decentralized finance (commonly known as DeFi) represents the first widespread application of smart contracts. DeFi utilizes smart contracts running on blockchain platforms (primarily Ethereum) to provide automated financial tools without relying on intermediaries such as brokers, exchanges, or banks. DeFi platforms enable individuals to borrow or lend funds, speculate on asset price movements with derivatives, trade cryptocurrencies, and earn interest through savings accounts[3]. In DEXs, only a minority of traded currencies are native blockchain assets (e.g., ETH), with most (the so-called tokens) being implemented by smart contracts running on Ethereum [4]. Beyond their role in value exchange and as part of the decentralized application (Dapp) ecosystem, tokens also serve as means for fundraising, booking, or investment, and for building ecosystems or communities. The greater the token's significance, the higher its value [5]. These tokens have involved substantial funds in decentralized exchanges, with the total market capitalization of the top twenty most active tokens on Ethereum exceeding 20.6 billion USD as of June 2024.

To facilitate the exchange of native tokens and those implemented by smart contracts in DEXs, Ethereum developers introduced the Ethereum Request for Comment-20 (ERC-20) homogenized token standard [6]. This standard specifies the attributes that tokens must implement, ensuring that each token is identical in type and value to another, thus enabling different tokens to interact in a consistent and compatible manner within the Ethereum ecosystem. However, DEXs (like the popular Uniswap in Ethereum) do not

conduct contract audits on ERC-20 tokens deployed within them. Any token that meets the ERC-20 standard can be deployed, and developers may even deploy without uploading the contract's source code, simply by depositing a pair of ERC-20 tokens into the trading pool to provide liquidity. This has led to the existence of a large number of honeypot ERC20 contracts in DEXs designed to steal traders' assets [7].

Currently, detection methods for closed-source honeypot ERC20 contracts are primarily divided into two categories: first, utilizing external tools to perform static analysis on contract bytecode; second, using the estimateGas method provided by EVM (to estimate the gas fee needed for a transaction) to verify whether the token's purchase, authorization, and sale operations can be executed within a transaction. However, existing static analysis tools often focus on detecting vulnerabilities such as integer overflow and reentrancy. They also face performance issues due to limitations in recursive depth, often taking several minutes to analyze a contract. The main limitation of using the estimateGas method to check for honeypot risks is its inability to detect contracts with a honeypot toggle mechanism, which is akin to black-box testing and only detects contracts without such toggles. Furthermore, the results of both methods are independent of the blockchain, preventing other traders from immediately understanding the risk associated with a contract.

This study proposes an innovative solution: integrating the honeypot contract detection system into the Ethereum execution client. The advantage of this integrated approach is the ability to timely identify and address contracts posing honeypot risks. The detection system verifies that the contract is an ERC20 standard by its address, retrieves the contract bytecode, and converts it into EVM opcodes. It then locates the entry point of the transfer method, simulates the execution of contract opcodes, and checks for scenarios matching predefined honeypot contract patterns. By analyzing opcodes directly within the Ethereum execution client without relying on on-chain contract interaction records, the system focuses on the contract's Transfer method, thereby enhancing detection efficiency. Additionally, Ethereum full nodes running the integrated detection tool can flag contracts posing honeypot risks. This method helps strengthen the entire Ethereum network's ability to discern ERC20 honeypot contracts, providing stronger security for the Ethereum blockchain ecosystem.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the basic concepts of Ethereum, smart contracts, and honeypot tokens to establish

the research background. Section 3 discusses in detail the related research on honeypot contract detection and its limitations. Section 4 describes the design and implementation process of the detection algorithm proposed in this study. Section 5 evaluates the efficiency and accuracy of the proposed detection system. Section 6 discusses potential improvements and outlines future research directions.

2. BACKGROUND

In this section, we introduce the fundamental concepts related to this study and briefly explain the definitions and implementation methods of Ethereum, smart contract, ERC20 fungible token standard, and ERC20 honeypot contracts.

2.1. *Ethereum*

Ethereum can be viewed as a state machine that undergoes a state transition when the latest block containing transactions is added to the chain. It uses the Merkle Patricia Trie (MPT) data structure to maintain a state tree that stores all account information, Ether balances, and smart contract codes. To ensure consistency in state transitions across all mainnet nodes, transactions are executed based on the state stored in the state tree of the previous block. In Ethereum's design, any operation that changes the state of the blockchain is considered a transaction. Due to the immutable ledger nature of the blockchain, any transactions added to the chain are irreversible [8].

The Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) is a distributed state machine within Ethereum, responsible for executing smart contract code. It is Turing complete, ensuring that code is executed consistently on any node within the Ethereum network. The EVM is a crucial component for managing smart contracts and executing transactions on Ethereum.

2.2. *Smart Contract*

Compared to Bitcoin, Ethereum possesses nearly Turing-complete smart contract capabilities [9]. Smart contracts play a key role in the Ethereum ecosystem. Essentially, they convert various agreements that parties agree to abide by into code, existing digitally on the Ethereum blockchain. These contracts are transparently accessible, allowing for trustable transactions without third-party oversight, and are traceable and irreversible.

Smart contracts are developed in high-level languages (such as Solidity) and compiled into EVM bytecode, which is then deployed on the blockchain. The EVM decodes it into opcodes, which are subsequently executed according to predefined program logic to realize the logic and functions defined in the smart contract. When executing smart contracts, the EVM maintains a runtime stack, memory as temporary space, and storage as permanent space for data storage [10].

A major advantage of smart contracts is that they execute automatically when predefined conditions are met, ensuring immediate outcomes without the need for intermediaries. Automation is one of the key features of smart contracts, such as triggering subsequent actions after the current contract execution. The main advantages of smart contracts include fast execution (automatic upon conditions being met), high transparency (contract terms are publicly accessible), and enhanced security (decentralized and immutable post-execution) [11]. These characteristics make Ethereum smart contracts a key driver in promoting programmable, secure, and transparent blockchain applications. Thus, smart contracts are fundamental in the Ethereum ecosystem for building various decentralized applications, providing a platform for executing transactions and managing logic without intermediaries.

Currently, there are several blockchain platforms that support smart contracts [12], including but not limited to Ethereum, Hyperledger Fabric [13], and Corda. Among these platforms, Ethereum is the most renowned.

2.3. ERC20 Fungible Token Standard

The ERC20 token standard is a specification for implementing smart contracts on the Ethereum blockchain, primarily used for issuing and managing fungible tokens. Fungible tokens mean that each token is identical and indistinguishable from others, a characteristic that makes them widely applicable in the digital economy for representing currencies, point systems, or voting rights.

```
1 interface IERC20 {
2     function totalSupply() external view returns (uint256);
3     function balanceOf(address account) external view returns
4         (uint256);
5     function transfer(address to, uint256 value) external
6         returns (bool);
7     function allowance(address owner, address spender)
8         external view returns (uint256);
```

```

6     function approve(address spender, uint256 value) external
      returns (bool);
7     function transferFrom(address from, address to, uint256
value) external returns (bool);
8     event Transfer(address indexed from, address indexed to,
uint256 value);
9     event Approval(address indexed owner, address indexed
spender, uint256 value);
10 }

```

Listing 1: The interface that must be implemented by contracts that conform to the ERC20 token standard

As shown in Listing 1, this standard defines a series of API interfaces that must be implemented, including token transfer (`transfer`), viewing the token balance of any address (`balanceOf`), the total supply of tokens (`totalSupply`), two functions for authorizing a third party to transfer tokens on behalf of the token holder (`approve` and `transferFrom`), and two event declaration methods (`Transfer` and `Approval`). The ERC20 standard requires that corresponding events occur whenever `transfer` and `approve` methods are executed [14]. The standardization of these interfaces ensures the interoperability of various smart contracts across different applications and wallets, allowing developers to create and deploy new digital assets while ensuring interoperability and compatibility.

The ERC20 standard also provides important security features for token transactions, such as preventing tokens from being accidentally sent to non-ERC20 contract addresses. Additionally, due to its simplicity and clarity of functions, ERC20 tokens can be easily integrated with other smart contracts and decentralized applications, facilitating the development of the decentralized finance (DeFi) ecosystem.

Since the launch of the ERC20 standard, it has become one of the most popular and successful token standards on Ethereum. Many well-known digital assets, such as USDT and BNB tokens, are created based on the ERC20 standard. The success of this standard has also driven other blockchain platforms to develop similar token standards, further enriching the application scenarios of the entire blockchain industry.

2.4. ERC20 Honeypot Contracts

An ERC20 honeypot contract is defined based on three criteria: 1. Creation of a liquidity pool in a decentralized exchange (DEX) paired with a valuable token. 2. Compliance with the ERC20 fungible token standard. 3.

Victims can purchase the token in a DEX but are unable to sell it back in the DEX. Figure 1 illustrates the process of fraud executed by an ERC20

Figure 1: ERC20 Honeypot Contract Fraud Process.

honeypot contract. Initially, the attacker deploys a smart contract that conforms to the ERC20 standard but includes special logic to prevent buyers from selling, allowing the contract to be deployed on a DEX and recognized by wallet software (such as MetaMask) as an ERC20 token. Subsequently, the attacker pairs this token with a valuable token (most commonly ETH) to create a trading pair and establishes a liquidity pool. The attacker then generates fake transactions [15] to create the illusion of increased trading volume and rising token prices, thereby attracting automated arbitrage bots involved in sandwich attacks [16] and victims seeking profit opportunities to buy the tokens. Ultimately, victims are unable to sell the tokens to retrieve ETH from the liquidity pool, and once a sufficient number of victims have bought the tokens, the attacker can profit by removing liquidity and extracting funds from the pool.

The core logic of an ERC20 honeypot contract is designed to prevent victims from selling their tokens and withdrawing valuable tokens, relying on special design features in the token smart contract. Depending on different user behaviors, ERC20 honeypot contracts can have various design strategies. In this section, the common implementations of ERC20 honeypot contracts will be explained in this section. Each type of trap can be realized through various code implementations, and attackers may obfuscate the core code to conceal their true intentions.

2.4.1. Blacklist

In this type of honeypot contract, victims can purchase ERC20 tokens deployed on a DEX, but they are often unable to sell them back. As shown in Listing 2, the attacker first implements the public transfer method specified by the ERC20 standard. Within this method, the `_transfer` internal method is called, where the actual token transfer logic is implemented. Unlike a harmless ERC20 contract, this contract includes an additional `_tendiesFactory` method to check a blacklist. This method initially verifies whether the to address of the transfer is the token's liquidity pool address within the DEX. If the to address is the liquidity pool address, the contract will check the boolean value in the `_blacklisted` mapping for the sender's address. If the mapping returns false, it will halt the execution of the transfer method and rolls back all operations.

In the example code, when buying tokens, the transfer method's sender address is the liquidity pool address, and the to address is the victim's address, which passes the blacklist check. When victims try to sell tokens, they first need to approve the DEX. The attacker overrides the approve method to add the caller's address to the blacklist mapping when it is called. When selling tokens, the sender address is the victim's address and the to address is the liquidity pool address, at which point the transfer method fails, preventing the victim from selling the tokens. This type of code allows normal transfers to other accounts when the to address is not the liquidity pool address, and only performs a blacklist check when the to address is the liquidity pool address.

```
1 mapping(address=>bool) private _blacklisted;
2 function transfer(address recipient, uint256 amount) public
  returns (bool) {
3     _transfer(_msgSender(), recipient, amount);
4     return true;
5 }
6 function _transfer(address sender, address recipient, uint256
  amount) internal {
7     require(sender != address(0), "ERC20: transfer from
  the zero address");
8     require(recipient != address(0), "ERC20: transfer to
  the zero address");
9     _tendiesFactory(sender, recipient, amount);
10    uint256 senderBalance = _balances[sender];
11    require(senderBalance >= amount, "ERC20: transfer
  amount exceeds balance");
```

```

12     _balances[sender] = senderBalance - amount;
13     _balances[recipient] += amount;
14     emit Transfer(sender, recipient, amount);
15 }
16 function _tendiesFactory(address from, address to, uint256
    amount) internal {
17     if(to == _belleToken) {
18         require(!_blacklisted[from], "Belle is for humans
    only!");
19     }
20 }

```

Listing 2: Black List ERC20 honeypot contract

Transfer Lock

In this type of honeypot contract, transaction locks targeted at specific accounts are in place. As depicted in Listing 3, the attacker first implements the public transfer method as specified by the ERC20 standard. Inside the transfer method, the `_transfer` internal method is called, where the core logic of the transfer is executed. Before performing the balance additions and subtractions, it checks the boolean mapping associated with the sender and to addresses. If the transaction lock's boolean mapping for either the sender or the to address is set to false, the method will halt execution and roll back.

```

1 mapping (address => bool) public frozenAccount;
2 function transfer(address recipient, uint256 amount) public
    returns (bool) {
3     _transfer(_msgSender(), recipient, amount);
4     return true;
5 }
6 function _transfer(address _from, address _to, uint _value)
    internal {
7     require (_to != address(0x0));
8     require (balanceOf[_from] >= _value);
9     require (balanceOf[_to] + _value >= balanceOf[_to]);
10    require(!frozenAccount[_from]);
11    require(!frozenAccount[_to]);
12    balanceOf[_from] -= _value;
13    balanceOf[_to] += _value;
14    emit Transfer(_from, _to, _value);
15 }

```

Listing 3: Transfer lock ERC20 honeypot contract

Proxy contract

This type of honeypot contract is essentially an upgradeable contract[17]. The primary function of these contracts is to delegate all calls to another address that houses the specific implementation of the smart contract. This structure allows for the contract logic to be upgraded or modified without changing the contract address.

```
1 receive() external payable virtual {
2     fallback();
3 }
4 fallback() external payable virtual {
5     fallback();
6 }
7 function fallback() internal virtual {
8     delegate(implementation());
9 }
10 function implementation() internal view virtual returns (
11     address) {
12     ...
13     let result := delegatecall(gas(), implementation, 0,
14     calldatasize(), 0, 0)
15 }
```

Listing 4: Proxy contract ERC20 Honeypot contract

As shown in Listing 4, the receive and fallback functions are designed to handle Ether (ETH) sent to the contract and calls that do not match any function signatures. The `_fallback` internal function delegates all calls to the implementation contract. The implementation function returns the current address of the implementation contract, and this address can be changed via a management function that only the contract owner can call. The delegate method utilizes the underlying `delegatecall` method to execute code from another address within the current contract. This structure can be used to conceal malicious behavior or obscure logic, as it allows for changing the behavior of the contract through swapping the implementation contract, making such changes difficult to detect.

3. RELATED WORK

Torres et al. [18] conducted pioneering work in analyzing honeypot smart contracts on Ethereum, identifying common implementation methods to define categories and developing the HONEYBADGER tool, which uses sym-

bolic execution and precise heuristic methods to automatically detect various types of honeypots. ZEUS[19] is a static analysis tool that combines abstract interpretation, symbolic model checking, and constraint statements to verify the safety of smart contracts without execution. However, ZEUS lacks involvement in mathematical equations and cross-function analysis, with limited runtime parameters, which may not capture dynamic behaviors during runtime. Slither[20] is a static analysis framework for Ethereum smart contracts, integrating data flow analysis and taint analysis. Oyente[21] helps developers identify and fix security vulnerabilities before deploying contracts by using symbolic execution and control flow graphs (CFG) to detect vulnerabilities within smart contracts. However, it may not be as flexible as dynamic analysis tools in updating and supporting new vulnerability patterns. Mythril[22], another static analysis tool for smart contracts, uses symbolic execution and control flow verification to detect common vulnerabilities like reentrancy and integer overflow. These tools focus on security issues in smart contracts, mainly targeting structural and behavioral vulnerabilities, but they do not address backdoor issues in ERC20 token contracts.

Chen Ting et al. [23] discovered that some token implementations in Ethereum did not strictly adhere to the ERC20 standard and proposed a method to detect inconsistent behaviors in ERC20 tokens by comparing the data structure of token quantity mapping for addresses and the token increase or decrease amounts declared in events. Ma Fuchen et al. [24] proposed a hybrid analysis method that combines data log analysis and fuzz testing to detect backdoor threats in ERC20 token contracts. Rundong Gan et al. [25] classified ERC20 honeypot contracts into five types based on attack effects and proposed a detection scheme based on historical data analysis and transaction simulation. Although these methods can reveal inconsistent behaviors and potential backdoor threats in ERC20 token contracts, they are conducted independently outside the blockchain system and require a lengthy processing time. These methods rely on event declarations generated after transactions are completed to analyze data, which means that potential issues and abnormal behaviors can only be detected after the transactions have occurred and been recorded on the blockchain. Therefore, these methods still have limitations in terms of prevention and handling time.

Chen Ting et al. [26] also proposed the Ethereum smart contract SODA detection framework, utilizing the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) to design a detection method suitable for smart contracts on any blockchain. Compared to online analysis detection methods, this framework shows significant

differences in efficiency and compatibility. By collecting information required to detect different attacks at the EVM level and integrating the detection application into the go-Ethereum client (Eth’s Golang implementation), this innovation not only significantly enhances analysis efficiency and addresses the issue of delayed detection results but also makes the framework easily portable to EVM-compatible public blockchains.

DETECTOR DESIGN

This study aims to develop a lightweight tool for detecting ERC20 honeypot contracts on the Ethereum blockchain and integrate it into servers running Ethereum full nodes. Compared to existing methods for detecting ERC20 honeypots, this approach significantly improves detection efficiency. Miners operating Ethereum full nodes can detect and flag new ERC20 contracts for honeypot risks during the block packaging process. As shown in

Figure 2: ERC20 honeypot contract detector architecture diagram.

Figure 2, during the startup process of the Ethereum client (geth), the detector service is registered when creating a full node is created. This includes constructing the structure of the detection components and then calling custom method APIs to register the application programming interfaces (API) of this tool. The method defines the API’s namespace, version, service instance, and visibility parameters. Considering that not all users running full nodes need to detect ERC20 honeypot contracts, to avoid unnecessary

memory overhead and maintain the efficiency of the full node, only the shut-down function of the detection component and the instances that pass the necessary parameters are registered, rather than a complete Ethereum client instance. Subsequently, in the geth interactive console, mappings for three methods in the detector are added: `detect.DetectSingle`, `detect.DetectBatch`, and `detect.StopDetectHoneyPots`. These methods are used to detect whether a contract address is a honeypot ERC20 contract (the parameter is the contract address), to detect whether a batch of contract addresses (the parameter is a String of contract addresses separated by commas) are honeypot ERC20 contracts, and to stop the honeypot ERC20 contract detection service respectively.

The `DetectSingle` and `DetectBatch` methods are for individual and batch detection of ERC20 honeypot contracts, respectively. Compared to the `DetectSingle` method, the `DetectBatch` method parses the string of contract addresses into an array of address types, then iteratively executes the detection logic found in `DetectSingle`. Therefore, the focus is mainly on the implementation logic of `DetectSingle`.

The `DetectSingle` method first ensures that the client instance is successfully initialized, facilitating the querying of contract bytecode at the corresponding address in the Ethereum client. After generating the log for this method call, it calls Ethereum's client-provided `CodeAt` method to obtain the contract bytecode. If the bytecode at the contract address is not empty, it will proceed to the core detection logic in the `controlFlowAnalyze` method for further analysis. After analysis is complete, the `logHoneyPots` method is called to print the results of the contract detection.

Because the implementation method of the honeypot is mainly based on the transfer method in ERC20, to detect honeypot risks in contracts, the `analyzeControlFlow` method within the detector specifically examines the control flow of the ERC20 transfer method. Before delving into the implementation logic of the `analyzeControlFlow` method, this study needs to clarify the difference between honeypot logic and normal logic at the opcode level. As depicted in Figure 3-a, during the invocation of the transfer method to execute token transfers, the contract receives a call `Calldata` containing the method signature and parameters. The execution logic first enters the function selector within the function wrapper. The function selector is designed to navigate to the corresponding control flow based on the function signature in the `Calldata`. If the function selector does not contain the function signature present in the `Calldata`, the call is considered illegal, and the

Figure 3: Function selector and function wrapper for transfer method.

execution enters a basic block containing the REVERT opcode, which then rolls back all operations. Upon entering the function selector basic block, the stack only contains the function signature of the transfer method. In this block, the transfer method’s signature is pushed onto the stack, followed by a comparison of the top stack element with the method signature. If they match, it proceeds to the control flow of the corresponding method. Thus, it is possible to enter the transfer method’s control flow by forging Calldata that includes the transfer method signature in the function selector section.

Upon entering the control flow of the transfer method, the detector proceeds to check the value in Calldata, as shown in the simplified opcode in Figure 3-b. Since the transfer method does not require receiving ETH, Calldata that includes ETH is regarded as an illegal call. In this basic block, the Calldata’s ETH value is first retrieved. If the value is 0, it moves to the next block. However, if the value is not 0, it enters a basic block containing the REVERT opcode and rolls back all operations.

After passing the value check, the detection system proceeds to check the length of Calldata. In Ethereum, a function signature occupies 4 bytes, and each parameter within the method takes up 32 bytes. Thus, for the transfer method, which includes two parameters, the Calldata length must be at least 68 bytes. As depicted in Figure 3-c with the simplified opcode, the basic block first pushes 0x04 onto the stack and then the Calldata length. It then performs a SUB operation to obtain the length of the Calldata parameters

and compares it with 0x40 (the combined length of two parameters). If the parameter length exceeds that of two parameters, the execution moves out of the function wrapper and into the transfer function body. If the Calldata parameter length is less than the length of two parameters, it enters a basic block containing the REVERT opcode and rolls back all operations.

If the jump to position 0x0654 proceeds normally, it indicates that the Calldata sent with this call is valid, and the contract then enters its normal detection logic.

```

1 require(sender != address(0));
2 require(to != address(0));
3 require(balanceOf[sender] >= amount);
4 require(balanceOf[to]+amount >= balanceOf[to]);

```

Listing 5: Legal check in ERC20 transfer method.

Figure 4: The opcode basic block corresponding to the legal check in Listing 5.

We have summarized several scenarios of normal checks within the ERC20 contract’s transfer method. As shown in Listing 5, the first steps involve checking the sender and to addresses. Lines 1 and 2 of Listing 5 correspond to the simplified opcode in Figure 4-a, with the stack’s top element being the sender address upon execution of the first line of code and the to address upon executing the second line. The basic block first pushes 0 onto the stack and then uses the EQ opcode to compare it with the address. If the top stack element equals 0, it enters the REVERT basic block to roll back; otherwise, it jumps normally to the basic block 0x0dc3 to continue execution.

After checking the address, the process moves to check the sender's address balance. This step verifies whether the sender address owns fewer tokens than the amount of tokens to be transferred. The code on line 3 of Listing 5 corresponds to the simplified opcode in Figure 4-b. In the first step, the sender's address is pushed onto the stack and stored in memory from position 0x00 to 0x20. In the second step, 0x02 is stored in memory from position 0x20 to 0x40. In the third step, the KECCAK256 opcode is executed to hash the two elements stored in memory from 0x00 to 0x40. In the fourth step, the value stored in storage at the index given by this hash, which is the token balance of the sender's address, is read. In the fifth step, the amount of tokens to be transferred, the second parameter in the Calldata, is pushed onto the stack. If the amount is greater than the token balance of the sender's address, execution moves to the REVERT basic block to roll back; otherwise, it proceeds to the basic block at 0x0e1a to continue execution.

After checking the sender's address balance, the process moves to checking the to address balance. This step ensures that the total number of tokens owned by the recipient plus the tokens to be transferred will not overflow, as there is a limit due to the fixed-size data type used to store token values. The code on line 4 of Listing 5 corresponds to the simplified opcode in Figure 4-c. In the first step, the sender address is pushed onto the stack and stored in memory from position 0x00 to 0x20. In the second step, 0x02 is stored in memory from position 0x20 to 0x40. In the third step, the KECCAK256 opcode is executed to hash the two elements stored in memory from 0x00 to 0x40. In the fourth step, the value stored in storage at the index given by this hash, which is the token balance of the to address, is read. In the fifth step, the amount of tokens to be transferred, the second parameter in the Calldata, is pushed onto the stack and added to the to address's token balance. If the result is less than or equal to the to address's token balance, execution moves to the REVERT basic block to roll back; otherwise, it proceeds to the basic block at 0x0eb5 to continue execution.

This study has found that when analyzing the code and corresponding opcodes for normal legitimacy checks, the balanceOf[address] code corresponds to opcodes that first hash the address combined with 0x02. This hash value is used as the index in storage to store the token balance corresponding to this address. Typically, to distinguish between different mappings that point to the same index (usually an address), the EVM hashes the address combined with a 1-byte number to use as the index value.

This study focuses on the conditions in the transfer method that lead

to rollback operations. Contracts containing code blocks that perform non-standard instrumentation are considered honeypot contracts.

```

1 PUSH1 0x07
2 ...
3 SLOAD
4 ...
5 EQ
6 ISZERO
7 PUSH2 0x103a
8 *JUMPI

```

Listing 6: The opcode corresponding to line 17 in Listing 2.

In Listing 2, the key logic for implementing a honeypot is located at lines 17-18, with the corresponding opcode block in line 17 simplified as shown in Listing 6. At this point, the top element on the stack is the to address. Since `_belleToken` variable is an address-type variable written to storage by other methods within the contract, it can be read by calling the `SLOAD` method to fetch the data from storage and then comparing it with the to address. If the to address does not match the element at storage position `0x07`, the control flow jumps to the basic block at position `0x103a`. Otherwise, it proceeds to the next block in sequence. The opcode block can be reduced to the following code in Listing 7:

```

1 If((to!=storage[0x07]) ){
2   JUMP TO 0x103A
3 }else{
4   Next OPCODE
5 }

```

Listing 7: Control flow jump logic in Listing 6.

Therefore, it is important to note whether the condition for the `JUMPI` opcode to jump is related to the comparison result of the to address and the element retrieved from the storage (indexed by the value pushed by `PUSH1`). If it is related, it means that the control flow will go in two directions depending on whether the to address is the same as or different from the element at the specified storage location. When both the `IsToTainted` taint value and the `PUSH1data` taint value are true, it is possible to determine the direction of the control flow. Setting the `toAddressCheck` taint to true under these circumstances facilitates subsequent analysis of blacklist honeypot logic.

```

1 PUSH1 0x00
2 ...
3 DUP2
4 MSTORE
5 PUSH1 0x20
6 PUSH1 0x06

```

```

7 MSTORE
8 ...
9 PUSH1 0x40
10 PUSH1 0x00
11 KECCAK256
12 SLOAD
13 ...
14 PUSH1 0xff
15 AND
16 PUSH2 0x103A
17 *JUMPI

```

Listing 8: The opcode corresponding to line 18 in Listing 2.

The opcode basic block corresponding to line 18 code in Listing 2 is simplified as shown in Listing 8. At this time, the top element of the stack is the sender address. First, the MSTORE opcode is used to write the to address to the memory location 0x00 to 0x20, and then the MSTORE opcode is used again to write 0x06 to the memory location 0x20 to 0x40. Then, the KECCAK256 opcode is used to merge the elements at locations 0x00 to 0x40 in the memory to obtain the hash, and finally the obtained value is ANDed with 0xff. If it is 0, jump to the basic block at location 0x103a, otherwise execute the next basic block in sequence. This opcode basic block can be converted into code in Listing 9:

```

1 If(0xff & storage[keccak256(memory[0x00:0x40])]){
2   Next OPCODE
3 }else{
4   JUMP TO 0x103A
5 }

```

Listing 9: Control flow jump logic in Listing 8.

Merge the corresponding codes of the two basic blocks to get in Listing 10:

```

1 If((to!=storage[0x07]) ){
2   JUMP TO 0x103A
3 }else{
4   If(0xff & storage[keccak256(memory[0x00:0x40])]){
5     Next OPCODE
6   }else{
7     JUMP TO 0x103A
8   }
9 }

```

Listing 10: Control flow jump logic in Listing 2.

When the first condition is not met, the control flow executed is the same as when both conditions are met. However, if only the first condition is met, the call is rolled back. Therefore, it is only necessary to focus on whether the jump condition of the JUMPI opcode is related to the value

in storage, which is obtained by combining the sender's address with the value pushed by PUSH1 and taking the hash value. Since this element is directly ANDed with 0xff as the condition of the JUMPI, it shows that the element can only be 0 or 1, confirming that the element is a Boolean value. It indicates that when the taint values for the IsCallerTainted, isPUSH1Data, and StorageValueIsBool are all true, a specific control flow path is determined, whereas other conditions lead to different paths. Under these circumstances, both control flows are explored. If one control flow direction contains a REVERT operation and the other proceeds normally to the next JUMPI opcode in the subsequent basic block, it suggests that the contract contains transfer lock honeypot logic.

```

1 PUSH1 0x00
2 ...
3 DUP2
4 MSTORE
5 ...
6 PUSH1 0x20
7 PUSH1 0x09
8 MSTORE
9 ...
10 PUSH1 0x40
11 PUSH1 0x00
12 KECCAK256
13 SLOAD
14 ...
15 PUSH1 0xff
16 AND
17 ISZERO
18 PUSH2 0x1812
19 *JUMPI

```

Listing 11: The opcode corresponding to line 10 and 11 in Listing 3.

The key logic of implementing the honeypot in Listing 3 is in lines 10 and 11. The corresponding opcode basic blocks of these two lines of code are simplified as shown in Listing 11. When running to line 10, the top element of the stack is the sender address, and when running to line 11, the top element of the stack is the to address. The first step is to write the top element of the stack to the memory position 0x00 to 0x20 through the MSTORE opcode. The second step is to write 0x09 to the memory position 0x20 to 0x40 through the MSTORE opcode again. The third step is to add the elements at positions 0x00 to 0x40 in the memory to obtain the hash through the KECCAK256 opcode. The fourth step is to perform an AND operation on the obtained value and 0xff. If it is 0, jump to the basic block at position 0x1812. Otherwise, execution proceeds to the next basic block that contains the REVERT opcode. This opcode basic block can be reduced to code in Listing 12:

```

1 If(0xff & storage[keccak256(memory[0x00:0x40])]){
2     REVERT

```

```

3 }elseif
4     JUMP TO 0x1812
5 }

```

Listing 12: Control flow jump logic in Listing 3.

Thus, attention should only be paid to whether the condition for the JUMPI opcode’s jump is related to the storage element indexed by the hash resulting from combining the sender address with a value pushed by PUSH1. Since this element performs a direct AND operation with 0xff as the condition for JUMPI, it indicates that the element is a boolean (either 0 or 1). If relevant, it indicates that when the taint values for the sender/to address, isPUSH1Data, and StorageValueIsBool are all true, one control flow path is determined, while other scenarios lead to a different path. If one control flow direction contains a REVERT operation and the other continues normally, it suggests that the contract contains transfer lock honeypot logic. In Listing 4, the key logic for implementing a honeypot involves calling an external contract. Therefore, the focus is on identifying whether there are any of the following opcodes in the transfer control flow: DELEGATECALL, CALLCODE, STATICCALL, or CALL. The presence of any of these opcodes suggests that the contract involves external calls. Since external contracts are typically closed-source and do not adhere to the ERC20 standard, they cannot be directly inspected. Thus, detecting any of these four opcodes in the contract’s transfer flow indicates the presence of proxy contract honeypot risks.

As shown in Algorithm 1, in order to detect the three honeypot modes mentioned above, this study designs a pseudo-depth-first traversal method to analyze the control flow of the transfer method. Additionally, a simulated opcode execution method has been designed in combination with taint analysis to emulate the states of the stack, memory, and storage within the contract.

Opcode that marks the start of a basic block	JUMPDEST
Opcode that marks the end of a basic block	JUMP, JUMPI, STOP, REVERT, RETURN, SELFDESTRUCT

Table 1: Opcodes marking the beginning and end of a basic block.

Initially, the process verifies that the contract’s bytecode includes the six function signatures defined by the ERC20 standard. If present, the bytecode

Algorithm 1 Detect potential honeypot mechanisms in ERC20 contracts

```
1: Input: Bytecode  $B$  of an ERC20 contract
2: Output: Identification of potential honeypot threats
3: if containsERC20Method( $B$ ) then
4:    $blocks \leftarrow$  toBasicBlocks( $B$ )
5:    $entry \leftarrow$  findTransferFunctionEntry( $blocks$ )
6:   if  $entry \neq$  nil then
7:     Initialize Stack, Memory, Storage
8:      $flags \leftarrow$  new flags structure
9:     Call dfs( $entry$ , Stack, Memory, Storage,  $flags$ )
10:    logHoneypotContract( $flags$ )
11: procedure DFS( $currentEntry$ , Stack, Memory, Storage,  $flags$ )
12:    $nextEntry \leftarrow$  Stack[0]
13:   for each  $opcode$  in  $blocks.opcodes$  do
14:     Stack, Memory, Storage  $\leftarrow$  opcodeExecution(Stack, Memory,
Storage,  $opcode$ )
15:     if  $opcode$  is JUMPI then
16:       if hasTainted( $Stack$ ,  $Memory$ ,  $Storage$ ) then
17:         dfs( $opcode + 1$ , Stack, Memory, Storage,  $flags$ )
18:         if ExistBlacklist then
19:            $flags.isBlacklist \leftarrow$  true
20:         if ExistTransferLock then
21:            $flags.IsTransferLock \leftarrow$  true
22:       else
23:         dfs( $nextEntry$ , Stack, Memory, Storage,  $flags$ )
24:       else if  $opcode$  is JUMP then
25:         dfs( $nextEntry$ , Stack, Memory, Storage,  $flags$ )
26:       else if  $opcode$  is one of [STOP, RETURN, SELFDESTRUCT]
then
27:         return nil
28:       else if  $opcode$  is one of [DELEGATECALL, CALLCODE, STAT-
ICCALL, CALL] then
29:          $flags.IsProxyContract \leftarrow$  true
30:       return
```

is compiled into EVM opcodes and segmented into different basic blocks.

Table 1 lists the opcodes that signify the start and end of basic blocks. The JUMPDEST opcode is used to mark the target positions for JUMP or JUMPI. JUMP represents an unconditional jump to the position of the first element on the stack to continue execution. JUMPI indicates a conditional jump that proceeds to the position of the first stack element if the second stack element is non-zero. Otherwise, the next opcode is executed in sequence. STOP halts execution. REVERT rolls back all state changes. RETURN stops execution and returns data from memory, typically used after the completion of a function call. SELFDESTRUCT destroys the contract, removing the code and storage from the blockchain. In addition, we define two additional basic blocks: 1. When there are two consecutive JUMPDEST opcodes, the first JUMPDEST opcode is considered as a basic block. 2. Treat the INVALID opcode as a basic block in its own right. This opcode is used to indicate an illegal operation during program execution, which means the abnormal end of the program. This study designs a BasicBlockAnalysis structure for each basic block, which contains all the opcodes of the basic block, the program counter of the first opcode, the stack, memory and storage status after the basic block is executed, and the basic block depth.

Elements in the stack, memory, and storage are defined using the TaintedItem structure, where the first field is the value and all remaining fields are boolean values related to taints. The stack is initialized as an empty array of TaintedItem structures, memory is initialized as a mapping from uint64 to TaintedItem, and storage is initialized as a mapping from string to TaintedItem.

This study has found that control flow bifurcation only occurs in the JUMPI opcode. In order to avoid inefficient depth-first traversal, in cases where the honeypot taint values are not true, the control flow only jumps to the top element of the stack when executing JUMPI. In cases where honeypot taint values are true, both control flow directions are explored. Therefore, a pseudo-depth-first search (dfs) method was designed. This dfs method is designed to determine the direction of the control flow based on the honeypot taint values, facilitating further analysis to ascertain whether the contract contains honeypot logic. The process starts by finding the entry point to the transfer method to enter its control flow and simulate opcode execution. Upon entering the control flow, the simulation initializes the stack to contain only one element: the transfer method's function signature without any taints, with memory and storage initially empty. The dfs (depth-first search) method determines the direction of control flow only at the last opcode of

STOP,SELFDESTRUCT	The program ends due to non-honeypot, ending the simulated control flow.
JUMP	Unconditionally jump to the top element of the stack.
JUMPI	By default, the basic block jumps to the program counter position corresponding to the value of the top element of the stack. When the honeypot taint value of the jump condition element is true, the stack, memory, storage status and the jump address by default are saved, and then the next opcode is executed sequentially.
REVERT, ASSERT	First, mark the control flow branch as rollback, then read the stack, memory, storage status and default jump address saved by the most recent JUMPI to execute the control flow. When the next JUMPI opcode can be executed normally, mark the contract as a honeypot contract.
Opcode that marks the end of a basic block	Marks the end of the method call and jumps to the top element of the stack to continue execution.

Table 2: The relationship between the last opcode of a basic block and the direction of control flow.

each basic block, as detailed in Table 2:

When the last opcode in a basic block is STOP or SELFDESTRUCT, it indicates the end of the program.

When the last opcode is RETURN, it signifies the end of a method call; execution then continues at the position indicated by the top element of the stack.

When the last opcode is JUMP, it represents an unconditional jump. Execution jumps to the basic block at the program counter position corresponding to the value of the top stack element.

When the last opcode is JUMPI, it indicates a conditional jump. By default, it jumps to the basic block at the program counter position corresponding to the value of the top stack element. When the taint values for

the address check and the address mapping to a boolean are both true, the current stack, memory, and storage state, along with the default jump address, are saved. Then, the system then executes the opcodes in the next basic block.

When the execution reaches a REVERT or ASSERT opcode, the program immediately terminates and rolls back all operations from that call—key opcodes for implementing honeypot logic. When execute to a basic block that contains either the REVERT or ASSERT opcode, the first step is to check whether the taint value for the honeypot condition of the jump element is true. If the honeypot taint value is true, this control flow branch is marked for rollback. Subsequently, the system retrieves the stack, memory, and storage states saved from the most recent JUMPI operation, along with the default jump address, to execute the control flow. If the control flow can proceed normally to the next JUMPI opcode in the subsequent basic block, the contract will be marked as a honeypot contract corresponding to the true honeypot taint value.

The opcodeexecution method simulates opcode execution to emulate the states of the stack, memory, and storage. This method is designed to analyze taints to aid in determining the direction of control flow in the outer dfs method. Table 3 illustrates the simulation logic for stack execution concerning different opcodes within this method:

As shown in Table 4, this method also involves taint delivery to analyze whether there is predefined honeypot logic in the external method.

The detection process for these three types of ERC20 honeypot contracts can be summarized as follows: For blacklist honeypot contracts, the detection logic begins with the opcodeexecution method by checking whether the JUMPI jump condition involves a comparison between the to address and the value in storage, and whether this comparison results in two possible control flow paths. If such bifurcation is identified, the ToAddressCheck taint of the jump condition element is set to true. The second step examines whether there is an operation involving reading a boolean value from storage, indexed by the sender address, which could also result in bifurcating the control flow. If bifurcation is confirmed, the StorageValueIsBool taint of the jump condition element is set to true. In the outer DFS method, at the end of each basic block, if the ToAddressCheck taint is true, both potential control flow paths are explored, documenting directions pointing to points A and B. If the StorageValueIsBool taint is true, both paths are explored; if one path leads to execution termination and state rollback while the other points to

CALLER	Push the fake sender address into the stack.
CALLDATALOAD	When the value of the top element of the stack is 0x04, a fake to address is pushed into the stack. When the value of the top element of the stack is 0x24, a fake amount value is pushed into the stack.
CALLDATASIZE	Push 0x68 into the stack to represent the standard length of the transfer method Calldata.
MSTORE	It represents storing the top element of the stack at the specified memory location, popping the top two elements of the stack and storing the top element of the stack at the specified memory location.
MLOAD	Represents reading the element at the specified memory location into the stack, popping the top element of the stack and pushing the element at the specified memory location onto the stack.
SSTORE	It represents storing the top element of the stack in the position specified by storage, popping the top two elements of the stack and storing the top element of the stack in the position specified by storage.
SLOAD	Represents reading the element at the specified position in storage into the stack, popping the top element of the stack and pushing the element at the specified position in storage into the stack.
KECCAK256	It means to merge the values of the elements of the specified length storage space in the memory, take the hash and push it into the stack, pop the top two elements of the stack and push one element into the stack.
PUSH1-PUSH32	Pushes an element of the specified length onto the stack.
DUP1-DUP16	Copies the element at the corresponding position in the stack to the top of the stack.
SWAP1-SWAP16	Swap the elements at corresponding positions in the stack with the top element.
ADD, SUB, MUL, DIV, AND, LT, GT, EQ, SGT, SLT, EXP	Represents the operation of the corresponding opcode on the first and second elements at the top of the stack, pops the two top elements of the stack and pushes the result of the operation as an element into the stack.
ISZERO	Determine whether the top element of the stack is 0, pop the top element of the stack and push it into the stack 0 or 1.
POP	Pop the top element of the stack.
JUMPI	Used for conditional jumps. In the simulated execution stack method, only two elements are popped out and no control flow decisions are made.
JUMP	Used for unconditional jumps. In the simulated execution stack method, only one element is popped and does not participate in the control flow decision.
DELEGATECALL, CALLCODE, STAT-ICCALL, CALL	Used for external calls. When these opcodes are executed, the simulation execution control flow is stopped immediately and a report is returned that a proxy contract exists.

Table 3: Simulate the corresponding operations for different opcodes in the stack execution method.

CALLER	Set the tainted field IsCallerTainted to true.
CALLDATALOAD	When the value of the top element of the stack is 0x04, the taint field IsToTainted is set to true. When the value of the top element of the stack is 0x24, the taint field IsTransferValueTainted is set to true.
MSTORE	The element's value and taint are retained in memory.
MLOAD	The stack retains the value and taint of the element.
SSTORE	The value and taint of the element are retained in storage.
SLOAD	The value and taint of the element are retained in the stack. When the top element of the stack only satisfies the IsToAddressTainted taint field and the IsPush1data taint field is true, it is considered to read the balance of the to address. At this time, the token balance of the simulated to address is pushed into the stack as the value of the element. When the top element of the stack only satisfies the IsCallerTainted taint field and the IsPush1data taint field is true, it is considered to read the balance of the sender address. At this time, the token balance of the simulated sender address is pushed into the stack as the value of the element. When the IsCallerTainted, IsPUSH1Data, and StorageValueIsBool taint fields are true at the same time, it is considered to read the bool mapping of the sender address. When the IsToAddressTainted, IsPUSH1Data, and StorageValueIsBool taint fields are true at the same time, it is considered to read the bool mapping of the to address. In the latter two cases, the honeypot taint value is set to true, and the two branches of JUMPI are traversed in the outer method for honeypot analysis.
KECCAK256	The stack retains the taints of all elements in the corresponding memory length.
PUSH1-PUSH32	In case of PUSH1 set the isPUSH1Data taint of the element to true.
DUP1-DUP16	The stack retains the value and taint of the element.
SWAP1-SWAP16	The stack retains the value and taint of the element.
ADD, SUB, MUL, DIV, AND, LT, GT, EQ, SGT, SLT, EXP	If the taint of either element is true, the corresponding taint of the pushed element is true. If one element satisfies the IsToAddressTainted or IsCallerTainted taint value is true, and the other element satisfies the IsPUSH1Data taint value is true, set the StorageValueIsBool taint value to true. When processing the AND opcode, if one of the elements is 0xff, set the StorageValueIsBool taint to true. When processing the EQ opcode, if one of the elements isToAddressTainted taint value is true, and the other element IsPUSH1Data taint value is true, set the ToAddressCheck taint value to true.
ISZERO	If the taint of either element is true, the corresponding taint of the pushed element is true.

Table 4: Simulate taint transfer and analysis operations for different opcodes in stack execution methods.

A or B, the contract is considered to have a blacklist-type honeypot risk.

The detection process for transaction lock honeypot contracts also starts with the opcodeexecution method. It initially assesses whether an operation involves reading a boolean value from storage, which is indexed by the sender or to address. Whether this value will lead to two flows when used as a jump condition, the `StorageValueIsBool` taint of the jump condition element is set to true. At the end of each basic block, if the `StorageValueIsBool` taint is confirmed, both potential flow paths are explored. If one path leads to execution termination and state rollback, while the other points to a basic block without rollback opcodes, the contract is deemed to exhibit transaction lock honeypot risk.

For the detection of proxy contract honeypots, once the control flow contains `DELEGATECALL`, `CALLCODE`, `STATICCALL`, or `CALL` opcodes, it is considered that there is a proxy contract honeypot risk. At this point, the detection process is terminated.

This layered detection strategy enhances the detector’s modularity and facilitates the future integration of new predefined honeypot detection logic, thereby improving the system’s detection accuracy.

EVALUATION

This research has developed a lightweight ERC20 honeypot contract detector, implemented in approximately 1200 lines of Golang code, tested on a desktop equipped with an Intel Core i7 10700, 16GB of RAM, and a 2TB hard drive. The detector has been successfully integrated into full nodes using the snap synchronization mode and is capable of effectively detecting ERC20 honeypot contracts. Given that Ethereum is one of the most widely used EVM (Ethereum Virtual Machine) compatible chains, this detector can be easily integrated into other EVM-compatible chains. To our knowledge, there has been no previous work that specifically utilizes contract bytecode analysis of the transfer method’s control flow to detect honeypot contracts.

Uniswap V2, currently the most popular DEX on Ethereum, is often exploited by honeypot contract deployers who may add liquidity with minimal funds to create the illusion of token price appreciation. Thus, this study randomly selected tokens from 5031 liquidity pools in the Uniswap V2 factory contract, each comprising less than 1 ETH in liquidity. As shown in the second row of Table 5, we identified 17 contracts with blacklist patterns, 2183 with transfer lock patterns, and 3 with proxy contract honeypots.

We downloaded the bytecode of contracts known to have issues like GenerateToken, FreezeAccount, and DisableTransfer, which are similar to the blacklist and transfer lock issues we discovered. As shown in the third row of Table 5, a total of 189 honeypot contracts with various issues were identified; 65 of these contracts contained honeypot logic that allowed the contract owner to trade other people’s tokens, issue unlimited tokens, or arbitrarily destroy tokens. Since these types of honeypot implementations do not involve the ERC20 transfer method, our detector was unable to identify these specific types of honeypot logic. Out of the remaining 124 contracts that designed around the transfer method, our detector identified 109 as honeypots. Further manual analysis of the undetected attacks revealed that these contracts’ honeypot implementations often included a boolean global lock controlling the token’s transactions, as well as transaction locks targeting individual addresses through boolean mappings, increasing recursive complexity. These findings emphasize the importance of further optimizing the detection algorithm to enhance the capability to recognize complex contract logic, thus improving the reliability and effectiveness of honeypot detection in blockchain environments.

Number of contracts tested	Blacklisted	Transfer Locked	Proxy Contract
5031	17	2183	3
124	0	109	3

Table 5: The number of contracts detected and the number of different types of honeypot contracts detected.

As shown in Figure 5, the peak CPU usage of a full node during synchronization-only scenarios is nearly identical to when the detector is active. The average CPU usage is 1.31% during synchronization-only and increases to 6.5% when the detector is enabled. Considering that an average block contains fewer than 200 transactions, and most transactions are simple transfers not involving contracts, this indicates that integrating the detector into full nodes for monitoring newly created contracts in blocks is acceptable. This confirms that the performance overhead introduced by our detection system is negligible. The detector enhances security without significantly burdening system resources.

For the analysis of 5031 contracts, the total detection time was 49 seconds. Figure 6 shows the distribution of time taken to detect each contract.

Figure 5: CPU usage of the detector when it is turned on and off.

Figure 6: Time consumption for detecting each contract.

Contracts that took 6ms to detect accounted for 100 entries, representing 1.99% of the total. Contracts that took 7ms accounted for 855 entries or 17.00%. Those taking 8ms were 187 entries, making up 3.72%. Contracts processed in 9ms totaled 1157 entries or 23.00%, and those taking 10ms were the most numerous at 2359 entries, comprising 46.89% of the sample. Con-

tracts taking more than 10ms were 372 in number, making up 7.39% of the total. On average, each contract took 9.74 milliseconds to process. These statistics underscore the significant advantage in processing speed offered by the detector designed in this study, demonstrating its practicality and reliability in efficient contract detection.

Figure 7: The maximum depth of basic blocks traversed by each contract.

Figure 7 presents the results of basic block traversal depth analysis conducted on 5031 contracts. Among them, contracts with a traversal depth of 0 total 100, matching those that took 6ms to detect as indicated in Figure 6. Upon manual analysis, it was discovered that these 100 contracts did not fully adhere to the ERC20 standard, resulting in the detector’s inability to locate the entry point of the transfer method. The number of contracts with a traversal depth of 1 is 855, also matching the data for a 7ms detection time shown in Figure 6. These contracts declared a transfer method but did not implement any specific logic within the method, leading to an immediate cessation of the control flow upon entry. No contracts exhibited a traversal depth of 2 or 3, as the second and third basic blocks are primarily used for validating the legality of Calldata. Most honeypot logic executes immediately after the validation of Calldata, which explains the significant proportion of contracts with traversal depths of 5 and 6. There are 305 contracts with a traversal depth greater than 36, all reaching a depth of 500, indicating that the detector may have entered a loop during detection. To prevent excessive consumption of system resources, the detector actively terminates analysis

of these contracts. This phenomenon highlights deficiencies in the detector's handling of complex logic.

Overall, our experimental results not only affirm the accuracy and efficiency of our detection system but also emphasize its practicality in enhancing the security of the Ethereum ecosystem. Our system's ability to detect and analyze ERC20 honeypot contracts accurately and in real-time has been proven to be a valuable addition to the security of the Ethereum ecosystem. The detection system does not require exceptional computing power or specialized hardware, facilitating its adoption across a broader range of Ethereum nodes. This research validates our detection system as a viable solution to address the security challenges posed by ERC20 honeypot contracts.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we detailed the implementation methods of ERC20 honeypot contracts and categorized them into three types of threats. Subsequently, an ERC20 honeypot contract attack detection system built into Geth v1.13.14 was proposed, which focuses on analyzing the control flow of the transfer method in the ERC20 token standard. This system can detect these threats without requiring contract interaction records or the contract's source code. The average analysis time per contract is only 9.74 milliseconds. Additionally, the real-time detection of new contracts in the latest blocks for potential honeypot risks has a negligible impact on system performance. Performance optimizations ensure that the system can execute detection tasks quickly and accurately without affecting the normal operation of the Ethereum network. The system can be ported to other Ethereum Virtual Machine-compatible chains. The ERC20 honeypot contract detection system not only enhances the security of transactions within the Ethereum network but also provides important support for the network's healthy development and the protection of user assets. Compared to existing blockchain-independent static analysis methods, it achieves faster detection.

Future work will focus on a deeper analysis of ERC20 contracts involving complex recursive transfer restriction logic. Although this may present new challenges, it is expected to significantly improve the accuracy of the detector. This timely detection method will enable full nodes to more effectively identify and analyze potential ERC20 honeypot contracts in blocks, thereby taking appropriate preventive measures.

Author contributions

D.L. wrote the original draft and took charge of methodology; K.Z. was responsible for experiments and providing relevant data, H.S. supplied all conceptualization and experimental figures, and G.D. took charge of the supervision of the paper and ensured the quality of the paper.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data availability

The source code for the detector and the results of the ERC20 honeypot contracts detections that support the findings of this study is available in the Dataverse repository: <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/VQX3ZH>.

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